

Strain-Engineered Ir Shell Enhances Activity and Stability of Ir-Ru Catalysts for Water Electrolysis: An Operando Wide-Angle X-Ray Scattering Study

Tomáš Hrbek, Peter Kúš,* Jakub Drnec, Marta Mirolo, Hridya Nedumkulam, Isaac Martens, Jaroslava Nováková, Tomáš Skála, and Iva Matolínová

Ir-Ru alloys with high Ru content serve as stable and highly active catalysts for the Oxygen Evolution Reaction (OER) in Proton Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyzers (PEM-WEs), enabling efficient operation with low Ir loadings ($150 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$). Despite this, the mechanisms behind their enhanced stability remain unclear. In this study, operando Wide-Angle X-ray Scattering (WAXS) and ex situ techniques are utilized to investigate the structural evolution of these magnetron-sputtered alloys during a PEM-WE operation. The findings reveal that Ru leaches from the surface upon potential application, forming a dynamic Ir-Ru@IrO_x core-shell structure. The Ir shell, strained by the Ir-Ru core, maintains a lower oxidation state than pure Ir catalyst, leading to superior catalytic activity and stability. Remarkably, the Ir-Ru 25:75 catalyst demonstrates better stability over Ir-Ru 50:50, despite its higher Ru content, due to the better protection of the subsurface Ir and Ru from oxidation and dissolution. This study not only clarifies the performance-enhancing mechanisms of Ir-Ru catalysts but also suggests that other, more economical materials, such as Co or Ti, could serve as effective cores in Ir-M systems, offering a pathway to more cost-effective catalysts for PEM-WE applications.

due to its zero-waste combustion and extremely high gravimetric energy density, making it a suitable energy vector for the future.^[2] However, hydrogen is only environmentally beneficial if produced without CO₂ emissions, which can be achieved through the electrolysis of water using renewable energy, resulting in green hydrogen.^[3]

The current state-of-the-art Water Electrolyzers (WEs) use alkaline electrolytes; however, this technology only fulfills some of the performance, versatility, and hydrogen purity requirements to fully supply the green hydrogen demand. There are several other WE concepts, such as Anion Exchange Membrane WE (AEM-WE), Solid Oxide WE (SO-WE), and Proton Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyzers (PEM-WE). However, AEM-WE and SO-WE suffer from severe issues with the durability of the used materials and ionomers^[4] that must be

overcome by further development, which is reflected by their significantly lower industrial representation in comparison to PEM-WE and alkaline WE.^[4] At the same time, a massive rise in the demand for green hydrogen is expected in the upcoming years.^[5] PEM-WE technology stands out as a mature solution without the drawbacks of alkaline WE.^[6] Nevertheless, its main problem is the dependency on noble metals, typically Pt on the cathode (0.4 mg cm^{-2}) for the Hydrogen Evolution Reaction (HER) and Ir on the anode (2.5 mg cm^{-2}) for the Oxygen Evolution Reaction (OER).^[7] Primarily due to the meager amount of mined Ir per year (about eight tons) and its high prices, which are not expected to improve due to its scarcity in the Earth's crust, Ir is considered the bottleneck of the PEM-WEs mass production.^[8] Therefore, reducing the amount of Ir used in the PEM-WEs is a crucial task that will strongly impact the evolution of the green hydrogen market in the next decade.

Several strategies have been proposed to reduce Ir loading, focusing either on improving the catalyst's morphology and structure or utilizing alternative materials to pure Ir or its oxides.^[9] The state-of-the-art method of catalyst preparation is chemical synthesis and wet deposition of the ink containing the catalyst;^[6] however, this approach has limitations at low Ir loadings ($< 0.5 \text{ mg cm}^{-2}$) where the formed nanoparticle layers lack

1. Introduction

Reduction of CO₂ emissions is a common goal shared by many advanced economies in the world.^[1] Achieving this requires the complete replacement of fossil fuels with CO₂ emissions-free alternatives. Hydrogen is one of the most promising candidates

T. Hrbek, P. Kúš, H. Nedumkulam, J. Nováková, T. Skála, I. Matolínová
Faculty of Mathematics and Physics
Department of Surface and Plasma Science
Charles University
V Holešovičkách 2, Prague 180 00, Czech Republic
E-mail: peter.kus@mff.cuni.cz
J. Drnec, M. Mirolo, I. Martens
ESRF – The European Synchrotron
ID 31 Beamline, 71 Avenue des Martyrs, Grenoble 38043, France

 The ORCID identification number(s) for the author(s) of this article can be found under <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202403738>

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sufficient lateral conductivity for stable operation.^[10] Various research directions are being explored to address this issue, such as supporting the catalyst on a cheaper material (TiO₂,^[11] TiC,^[12] TaC,^[13] etc.), enhancing the PEM active surface area^[14] or completely replacing the nanoparticles with layers prepared by Physical Vapor Deposition (PVD) techniques.^[15] Concurrently, efforts are ongoing to identify new materials that can substitute pure Ir/IrO_x as the catalyst for the PEM-WEs anode.^[16] Although non-noble-metal catalysts, such as MnO_x,^[17] NiFeO_x,^[18] LaFeO₃^[19] are being considered; their current poor performance in the real PEM-WE systems means that it is unlikely that industries will use them in the actual devices in the coming years. Bimetallic Ir-M catalysts with metal M are much more promising; the resulting Ir-M catalyst yields comparable or higher activities as purely Ir-based catalysts, yet with much lower Ir loading, e.g., Ir-Ru^[20] or Ir-Ni.^[21]

In previous works, we introduced a sputter-etching treatment of PEM to enhance the active surface area without any added supports, using magnetron sputtering to modify the membrane and deposit Ir for OER.^[15] Subsequently, we employed magnetron sputtering to create a bimetallic Ir-Ru system with various Ir-Ru ratios and low-Ir-loadings (29–113 μg cm⁻²). Surprisingly, the Ir-Ru 25:75 composition outperformed Ir-Ru 50:50, despite containing less Ir.^[20] We integrated these two approaches to develop a bimetallic Ir-Ru 25:75 catalyst with a low-Ir-loading of 158 μg cm⁻², deposited on the sputter-etched membrane.^[22] This combination yielded excellent activity (1 A cm⁻² at 1.606 V, 80 °C) and stability over 1000 h of degradation at 1 A cm⁻². The observed degradation within the last 500 h was only 1.3 μV h⁻¹, accepted as a reasonable degradation rate even for PEM-WEs with high Ir loadings.^[23] The magnetron-sputtered Ir-Ru system demonstrates a non-trivial behavior, as only a small amount of Ir significantly enhances the electrochemical properties – pure Ru at the PEM-WE's anode degrades completely within seconds, while Ir-Ru 25:75 shows minimal degradation over a week of measurements. Ex situ X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) indicated that this stability is due to the structural interaction and strain between face-centered cubic (fcc) Ir and hexagonal close-packed (hcp) Ru.^[20] We did not observe the fcc phase in the Ir-Ru 25:75, while there were both fcc and hcp phases in the Ir-Ru 50:50 system, with the hcp phase disappearing during the electrochemical procedure.^[20]

The crystallographic structure of catalysts significantly affects their electronic structure,^[23] influencing their ability to bond with reactants/products/reaction intermediates, thereby determining catalytic activity.^[24] According to the Sabatier principle, an ideal binding energy exists between the catalysts and reactants/products/reaction intermediates, resulting in the best possible catalytic activity.^[25] Consequently, the catalyst's activity can be enhanced by tuning the crystallographic and thus electronic structure to reach this optimum.^[26] That is achievable by various methods, from the direct mechanical strain of the material^[26] via the strain achieved by disordered preparation^[27] to the formation of multimetallic alloys.^[28]

Numerous studies have successfully engineered the electronic structure for OER by employing strain-architecture mechanisms, including work on Ir-based,^[29–34] Ru-based,^[35,36] and Ir-Ru catalysts,^[37–41] directly prepared in a core-shell form. The enhanced activity of Ir in these studies is frequently attributed to electron transfer from the donor metal (M) to Ir, which improves

Figure 1. Electrochemical performance corrected on Ohmic resistance. The first graph from the top shows the voltage evolution under the set current density depicted in the second graph in galvanostatic mode. The last graph shows the corresponding temperature as measured by a probe inserted in the anode of the PEM-WE cell. For the ohmic correction, each step is corrected by the corresponding ohmic resistance value.

catalytic activity and reduces the degradation rate of Ir. This explains also why a mere Ir-Ru mixture without any strain does not lead to improved overall activity and stability.^[41,42]

We hypothesize that the excellent catalytic performance of Ir-Ru 25:75 mentioned above stems from the interaction between the Ir and Ru and the consequent formation of the strain – induced by the Ir-Ru interaction and possibly by the preparation method (magnetron sputtering). The strain is then expected to influence the Ir electronic structure. This paper focuses on confirming or refuting this hypothesis by *operando* Wide Angle X-ray Scattering (WAXS) and X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS). Our study utilizes a dedicated *operando* PEM-WE cell for WAXS measurements,^[43] compatible with the high-energy and high-intensity X-rays at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) in Grenoble. Consistent with our previous Rotating Disks Electrode (RDE) results, we observe both the hcp and fcc phases in Ir-Ru 50:50 and Ir-Ru 25:75 samples and their rapid changes, even though there is less of the fcc phase than expected from the atomic composition. This explains the absence of the fcc phase in our previous study on laboratory systems.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Electrochemical Performance

Since the structural changes of the catalyst are induced by the actual potential on the catalyst and not the potential lost in the form of Joule's heat,^[44] we present electrochemical data already corrected to Ohmic resistance in **Figure 1**, together with the evolution of temperature on the anode of the cell throughout the procedure. The corresponding degradation rates for each current

step of the procedure are presented in Table S1 (Supporting Information). The degradation rates of each sample are significantly reduced within the long 300 mA cm⁻² step. A value of Ohmic resistance from the corresponding PEIS was used to correct each step of the galvanostatic procedure to reflect the changes in the Ohmic resistance in time. The original uncorrected electrochemical performance is presented in Figure S1 (Supporting Information), and the Ohmic resistances at the corresponding voltages are in Figure S2 (Supporting Information). We explain the discrepancy in the Ohmic resistance between different catalysts by using unstable non-platinized Ti, no ion trap to stabilize the water purity, imperfect pressing of the catalyst, and differing cell assemblies affected by human elements. The Ohmic resistance of the cell does not significantly increase with time, and it tends to decrease with an increasing voltage of PEIS. This is typical behavior for sputter-etched membranes even in real single-cell systems,^[22] thus indicating proper operation of the *operando* cell. Figure 1 shows that the bimetallic Ir-Ru catalysts outperform the pure Ir catalyst: both studied Ir-Ru concentrations almost identically. This does not directly match the results from our previous work, where Ir-Ru 25:75 outperformed Ir-Ru 50:50.^[20] A detailed analysis of this phenomenon presented in the Supporting Information led to the clear conclusion that the different performance of the catalyst in the *operando* cell is connected to the different areas of the catalyst-PEM interface, which likely originates from the non-ideal construction/assembly of the *operando* cell and the different loading of the catalyst on each sample after activation and Ru leaching – as the capacitance increases with decreasing Ru content. Consequently, each catalyst has a different morphology after activation. If we correct for the catalyst-PEM interface capacitance, the resulting performance order corresponds to our previous published data showing the performance of MEA Ir-Ru 25:75 > MEA Ir-Ru 50:50 > MEA Ir 100,^[20,22] which also corresponds to the Tafel slopes order when normalized on the Ir content (Figure S4, Supporting Information). Most importantly, the bimetallic samples exhibit significantly better stability than pure Ru and much higher activity and lower Tafel slope than pure Ir (both normalized and non-normalized); thus, we expect that the topmost surface layer consists either of more active Ir, more stable Ru, or an alloy of both.

2.2. Ex Situ XPS, EDX, and STEM: The Active Phase?

To understand the Ir-Ru catalyst, we combined structural, spectroscopic, and microscopic techniques. The active topmost surface is likely to be an amorphous oxide;^[45,46] however, its properties are typically affected by the sublayer or the surface on which the oxide grows.^[47,48] Therefore, we have two main questions to answer: First, what is the active phase in the system (IrO_x, RuO_y, etc.), and second, how is it possible that it demonstrates atypical behavior for the phase (either IrO_x being more active or RuO_x more stable than expected)? The first question is addressed in this section, based on the ex situ chemical, elemental, and morphological composition at BOL and EOL, while the second question is covered in the next section, based on the ex situ and *operando* WAXS results.

The morphologies of all samples at BOL are almost identical, as shown in Figure S8 (Supporting Information) (SEM) and

Figure S9 (Supporting Information) (TEM). At BOL, all samples are mostly metallic and homogeneous, both in the surface/bulk comparison from XPS/EDX (Figure 2 and Table 1) and at the level of single fibers from EDX STEM (Figure S10, Supporting Information, Ir-Ru 25:75). There are regions with varying amounts of Ir and Ru due to the character of the magnetron co-sputtering method; however, there is no ordered dependence like core-shell structure or segregation on the surface. Chemically, at BOL, Ir is oxidized to the same extent as the bimetallic Ir-Ru samples (Table S2, Supporting Information), based on the fitted XPS spectra in Figures S11 and S12 (Supporting Information). XPS fitting was done as in our previous studies^[20,22,49] based on Table S3 (Supporting Information).

After the electrochemical procedure (Figures 1 and 10), we observed significant leaching of ruthenium (Figure 2 and Table 1), with 28% and 38% of Ru remaining for Ir-Ru 50:50 and Ir-Ru 25:75, respectively. Surprisingly, the samples remained mostly homogeneous on a large scale even after the electrochemical procedure, as suggested by comparing the surface (XPS) and bulk (EDX). The sampling depth (SD) for XPS for Al Kα₁ is roughly 5.3 nm for Ir or Ru.^[50] Consequently, this implies that the catalyst is homogeneously activated throughout the thickness of the sputtered layer, which implies good dispersion on the sputter-etched structure and porosity. Unfortunately, the actual active part of the surface is typically much thinner than 5.3 nm;^[6] therefore, this does not conclusively determine whether it is Ir or Ru that forms the active phase on the catalyst's surface.

2.3. Intermezzo: SRPES Measurement on a Complementary Ir-Ru System on Au Disks

The real surface of the material can be probed using SRPES with very low energies of photoelectrons, around 100 eV.^[50] Unfortunately, radiation damage and poor conductivity do not allow for measurement with SRPES directly on the etched membranes with the Ir-Ru catalysts. Therefore, we conducted the SRPES measurements on Au disks with the same Ir-Ru concentrations as in Table 1, before and after the electrochemical half-cell procedure described in.^[20] The potentials used are similar to those in the current study. While there is no direct translation between the half-cell and single-cell PEM-WE,^[51] we believe this model approach is vital to understanding the Ir-Ru system. All spectra were measured with different binding energies to provide a depth profile. From the Ru 3d spectra on clean samples (Figure S13, Supporting Information), we observe that after the electrochemical procedure, almost no Ru remains on the actual surface of the catalyst when probed at a sampling depth (SD) of 1.3 nm. The small amount of residual Ru is not located on the true surface of the catalyst, as confirmed by the more contaminated samples in Figure S14 (Supporting Information). The additional C and S contaminants (Figure S15, Supporting Information) further reduce the SD, allowing even more surface-sensitive measurements. Based on the SRPES data, no Ru is present closer than 1 nm from the catalyst's surface. SD is always calculated based on the mean free paths from,^[50] assuming the limit of 95% of the intensity. The amount of observed Ru then increases with the probing depth, confirming that the surface is Ru depleted. Interestingly, a significant part of the subsurface Ru appearing at

Figure 2. Comparison between the total elemental composition at the surface (XPS, SD \approx 5.3 nm) and in the whole bulk of the thin film (EDX, S \approx up to μ m) before and after the PEM-WE electrochemical procedure.

SD = 2.3 nm is metallic. This indicates that there is still some metallic Ru that is very close to the surface. We do not expect this Ru to participate in the reaction directly, as it would immediately oxidize due to its thermodynamic properties.^[52] However, it is close enough to the surface to affect the Ir. The Ir 4f spectra in Figure S16 (Supporting Information) confirm the presence of Ir on the very surface (SD = 1.3 nm), where this Ir is almost completely oxidized, as quantified in Table S4 (Supporting Information). For Ir-Ru 50:50, there is 13% of metallic Ir, while for Ir-Ru 25:75, 12%. The amount of metallic Ir increases with the SD, as visible in Figure S17 (Supporting Information). This increment is much faster for Ir-Ru 25:75, which suggests that the sample stays less affected by the electrochemistry in the deeper layers, meaning the Ir shell is protecting the Ru-rich core. Consequently, from the SRPES measurements on a complementary model system of Ir-Ru on the Au disk, we conclude that the actual active species in our system are oxides of Ir since there is no Ru present in the topmost 1 nm of the surface and the Ir present is strongly oxidized.

2.4. Ex situ XPS, EDX, and STEM: Ir-Ru@IrO_x Core-Shell

Based on the SRPES from model Ir-Ru samples, we concluded that our system is a core-shell Ir-Ru@IrO_x, formed dynamically due to the applied potential. The core is a mixture of metallic and oxidic Ir-Ru. However, we should also discuss whether this can be concluded about our real-life PEM-WE catalyst on the sputter-

etched membrane. One crucial difference between the single-cell PEM-WE and half-cell measurements is the electrical contact of the catalyst: the usage of the porous LGDL in PEM-WE leads to the presence of areas with poor electric contact.^[22] Consequently, we expect more metallic Ir and Ru in the EOL samples from PEM-WE compared to the model samples, as shown in Figure 3. With this in mind, we can compare the chemical states of the highest SD from SRPES in Figures S13 and S14 (Supporting Information) (3 and 2.3 nm for Ir and Ru, respectively) with the XPS (5.3 nm) in Figure 2. In the combined Figure S16 (Supporting Information), we see that, principally, the chemical state at the EOL from PEM-WE is very similar to the model samples after electrochemistry, which bridges the PEM-WE system with the model one. The hypothesis of the core-shell structure is also backed by the EDX STEM line scan (Figure S18, Supporting Information), where we see an almost total absence of Ru at the very edge of the particle, which is a strong sign of a formed Ir-Ru@IrO_x core-shell structure.

Table 1. Atomic ratios of Ir and Ru from the bimetallic samples, measured by EDX (whole layer volume) and XPS with SD = 5.3 nm.

Sample	EDX before		XPS before		EDX after		XPS after	
	Ir	Ru	Ir	Ru	Ir	Ru	Ir	Ru
Ir-Ru 50:50	0.48	0.52	0.44	0.56	0.69	0.31	0.72	0.28
Ir-Ru 25:75	0.24	0.76	0.26	0.74	0.54	0.46	0.62	0.38

Figure 3. The XPS spectra measured at EOL, demonstrate significant electrochemical changes. a) Ir 4f spectra with labeled fitted states. b) Fitted Ru 3d and C 1s spectra with labeled fitted states.

Consequently, we answered our first question: when measured ex situ XPS at EOL, the active phase in the bimetallic Ir-Ru system is a mixture of Ir^{III} and Ir^{IV} (Figure 3). Those phases form a shell around a Ru-rich core, where the amount of Ru increases with the depth. Here, we see a significant difference between the bimetallic samples: With the increasing sampling depth SD, the metallic content of Ir is much higher for Ir-Ru 25:75 than for Ir-Ru 50:50 (Figure S17, Supporting Information). This means that the shell in the case of Ir-Ru 25:75 protects the inner parts of the catalyst much better than in Ir-Ru 50:50, which hints at the better stability of Ir-Ru 25:75.^[20,22] The biggest mystery at this point is the significantly better activity of the Ir-Ru-based catalysts. Since they have a pure Ir shell, they should show the same electrochemical performance as the pure Ir samples. However, this is not the case (Figure 1), and the bimetallic Ir-Ru catalyst works much better, simultaneously by the metrics of the onset potential, Tafel slope, and the total currents.^[20,22] This means that the subsurface Ru must affect the surface Ir layer.

XPS allows us to study the electronic structure of the catalyst. As shown in Figure 3, the relative amount of oxidized Ir decreases with increasing Ru content, which is quantified in Table S5 (Supporting Information). Specifically, Ir-Ru 25:75 contains only 42% oxidized Ir, while Ir-Ru 50:50 has 59%, and Ir 100 has 67%. Notably, the difference between Ir-Ru 25:75 and the other samples lies in both Ir^{IV} and Ir^{III} oxides. Ir-Ru 50:50 and Ir 100 have similar Ir^{IV} content, but Ir 100 contains significantly more Ir^{III}. These results are consistent with SRPES data from the model Ir-Ru system (Table S4), indicating that the presence of Ru in the subsurface region stabilizes the Ir shell in a lower oxidation state. This correlates well with the observed activity and stability trends in single-cell performance,^[20] where Ir-Ru 25:75 shows the best performance, as lower oxidation states of Ir are known to enhance OER.^[34,53,54] Previous studies and theoretical calculations suggest

that Ru's presence increases Ir's electronegativity, causing electron accumulation in Ir and preventing higher oxidation states, thus improving both stability and activity.^[38] However, this does not explain why Ir-Ru 50:50 performs disproportionately worse than Ir-Ru 25:75, both in electrochemical performance and in stabilizing Ir in lower oxidation states. To understand this, we need to examine how the catalyst changes upon activation, which is ideally suited for operando WAXS analysis.

2.5. Structure of the Ir-Ru Catalyst at First Scan in the Operando WAXS Cell

Our goal is to investigate the structure of the Ir-Ru catalyst and determine if and how it causes the lowering of the oxidation state of the Ir shell and, consequently also, its activity and stability.

First, we examine the structural properties of the catalysts as measured after the insertion into the operando cell before applying any potential. An example of the obtained diffractogram from the first scan is shown in Figure 4, with the marked region of Rietveld analysis. The diffractograms directly illustrate the differences between the tested MEAs, as defined in Table 2. A detailed view of one region at angles 7.25° to 9.25° with the theoretical diffraction lines for Ir, Ru, and Pt is shown in Figure S20 (Supporting Information). We refer only to the fcc and hcp phases for Ir and Ru for clarity and conciseness. Unless we specifically denote the fcc Pt phase from the cathode GDE, it is not considered in the discussion.

The dependency of the lattice parameters on the elemental composition is plotted in Figure 5, with the values corresponding to the bulk fcc Ir^[55] and hcp Ru^[56] (marked in the figure with tables), as well as to the hypothetical values of fcc Ru^[57] and hcp Ir^[57] (labelled as calculated). With the decreasing amount of

Table 2. Parameters of the anode side of prepared MEAs. Load_{Ir} stands for the upper estimation of Ir loading, Load_{Ru} for the upper estimation of Ru loading, and thickness for the equivalent thickness of the layer deposited on a flat surface.

Sample	Catalyst anode	LGDL anode	GDE cathode	Load _{Ir} [$\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$]	Load _{Ru} [$\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$]	Thickness [nm]
Ir 100	Ir	Ti	C + Pt	293	0	130
Ir-Ru 50:50	Ir-Ru	Ti	C + Pt	147	80	130
Ir-Ru 25:75	Ir-Ru	Ti	C + Pt	74	120	130
Ru 100	Ru	Ti	C + Pt	0	159	130

Ir, the fcc lattice parameter *a* downshifts toward the hypothetical value of fcc Ru. Simultaneously, the lattice parameter *a* of the hcp phase remains constant within its error bars, and the lattice parameter *c* of the hcp phase decreases with the decreasing amount of Ir shifting from the value of hypothetical Ir hcp structure to the value of bulk hcp Ru. This indicates that the fcc and hcp phases influence each other as the composition of Ir and Ru changes.

To quantify this effect, we calculated the expected composition of the Ir-Ru samples based on the shifts of the lattice parameters between the parameter *a* of fcc Ir/fcc Ru and *c* parameter of hcp Ir/hcp Ru, using Vegard's law approximation (Equation S2, Supporting Information).^[58] The results are plotted in Figure 6, together with the fcc and hcp phase content dependency on elemental composition. The parameters *a* of the hcp phase were not used in the calculations due to their proximity for hcp Ir (2.71 Å) and hcp Ru (2.704 Å). In summary, Vegard's law applies very well to the parameter *a* of the fcc phase and the parameter *c* of the hcp phase. Moreover, while the parameter *a* of the hcp phase does not

Figure 4. Diffractogram from the tested MEAs in the operando cell before applying any potential with the inset for the region fitted by Rietveld refinement with plotted diffraction lines calculated from the used .cif files for Ir mp-101 (dark blue), Ru mp-33 (dark red), and Pt mp-126 (dark green). Only lines with an intensity higher than 10% of the maximum diffraction intensity are shown. The measurement has been performed using synchrotron radiation at 75 keV.

Figure 5. The lattice parameter evolution of fcc and hcp phase for the first scan in the operando cell.

Figure 6. The evolution of fcc and hcp phase relative content in the operando cell before applying potential. Pt phase is not considered in this ratio. The Ir and Ru amounts are calculated from EDX measurements and from Vegard's law calculations.

contradict Vegard's law, it is not measured with sufficient precision to confirm it directly. Consequently, the Ir-Ru forms an alloy with properties dependent on the catalyst's composition.

The fact that the lattice parameters follow precisely Vegard's law toward the non-thermodynamically favorable fcc Ru/hcp Ir phases strongly suggests their actual presence in the system. However, it does not conclusively prove it. Considering the total amount of fcc and hcp phases plotted in Figure 6, we observe a higher amount of hcp phase than expected from the Ru content in the sample. Consequently, we believe this phase originates from hcp Ir. By calculating the difference between the total hcp phase content and the Ru content in Figure 6, we determine at least 13.3% and 11.3% of the hcp Ir in the Ir-Ru 50:50 and Ir-Ru 25:75 samples, respectively. This value is a minimum estimation, higher content of the hcp Ru is possible if fcc Ru is also present in the sample.

These conclusions hold only if we assume that the imbalance between the fcc and hcp phase is not due to a significantly higher amount of amorphous Ir oxides compared to Ru oxides. This is unlikely since Ir is generally more stable than Ru.^[52] Moreover, this assumption can be easily verified using XPS at BOL, as shown in Figures S11, S12 and Table S2 (Supporting Information). From the fits, roughly 20% of Ir and Ru are oxidized in the mixed samples at BOL. Complete oxidation levels are in Table S1 (Supporting Information); Ru oxidizes on the same or higher level than Ir, within the error margin.

The formation of hcp Ir was observed in the past by alloying with hcp Os^[59] or by straining the Ir structure by metastable hcp Ni.^[47] Since the lattice parameters of the hcp Ni ($a = 2.651 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 4.343 \text{ \AA}$)^[60] and hcp Ru ($a = 2.704 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 4.4038 \text{ \AA}$)^[61] are quite similar, this provides a plausible explanation for our case. Additionally, we note the similar behavior of the lattice parameters in our Ir-Ru system compared to the cited Ir-Ni system^[60] In that system, the hcp Ir component has a higher lattice parameter than hcp Ni. Still, it is downshifted compared to the calculated hcp Ir, similar to the behavior observed in our Ir-Ru system. Furthermore, the study by Geng et al.^[47] associates the presence of hcp Ir with a higher amount of oxidized Ir, which aligns well with the Ir versus Ir-Ru oxidation XPS results in Table S2 (Supporting Information).

The hcp Ir demonstrates better activity toward H₂O adsorption and dissociation,^[47] which, according to the corresponding Volcano plot for OER,^[62] leads to the enhanced activity of Ir for OER. Consequently, possible Ir oxides grown from the hcp Ir could exhibit higher activity than fcc Ir, thereby explaining our observed enhanced Ir activity. However, practically, the important conclusion is that the Ir metallic phase is significantly compressively strained by the present Ru at the beginning of the electrochemical procedure, which is known to have a direct effect on the electronic structure and a positive effect on the OER activity.^[63]

Complementary WAXS measurements of the samples ex situ confirm the trend observed in the *operando* cell (Figures S21 and S22, Supporting Information), thus justifying the fitting of the platinum fcc phase in the case of *operando* cell data. The *operando* data lattice parameter values are upshifted compared to the ex situ data by 0.05–0.1 Å. We attribute this to a combination of heat expansion (the cell operates at 50 °C),^[61,64] the strain caused by water absorption in the cell,^[65] and possibly by phase variations in the used X-rays in that time frame, as the

Figure 7. The evolution of lattice parameter a , and phase content for the fcc phase measured at the middle land, with applied potential. The states at BOL before applying any potential without potential are plotted as separated scatter points at Time = 0.

ex situ data were collected earlier than the rest of the *operando* measurements.

2.6. Ir-Ru Catalyst Structure Evolution Under Potential

The as-prepared catalyst structure is often quite dissimilar to the actual active structure formed in the working catalyst.^[66] This is the case for the sputtered Ir-Ru catalyst, as no core-shell structure was observed in the as-prepared samples. Therefore, our goal is to determine if and how the structure of the catalyst changes during the applied procedure from Figure 10 and if it supports our hypothesis of a strain-induced active Ir-Ru@O_x core-shell, introduced in the previous chapters. First, we use the data measured at the middle land under potential; later, we also comment on the supplementary results from the edge land. For all diffractograms, the Pt fcc phase was fitted separately and did not affect the resulting lattice parameters, except for the phase content; therefore, if we discuss the fcc phase, only the phase coming from Ir-Ru is considered if not stated otherwise.

Figures 7 and 8 illustrate the evolution of the fcc and hcp lattice parameters/phases, respectively. The values from the initial OCV scan are included for reference. In the case of the fcc phase, there is an upshift of the parameter a by 0.004, 0.008, and 0.001 Å for Ir 100, Ir-Ru 50:50, and Ir-Ru 25:75, respectively, thus suggesting that the fcc phase is the least affected by the potential in the Ir-Ru 25:75 sample and the most affected in Ir-Ru 50:50 sample. The hcp lattice parameters are almost completely constant stable for Ir-Ru 25:75, except for the slow decrement of the hcp phase, which likely corresponds to the dissolution and oxidation of Ru. On the other hand, the Ir-Ru 50:50 catalyst shows significant changes: immediately after the potential is applied, the strain on the fcc phase disappears, and the value of the lattice

Figure 8. The evolution of lattice parameters *a* and *c*, and phase content for the hcp phase measured at the middle land, with applied potential. The states at BOL before applying any potential without potential are plotted as separated scatter points at Time = 0.

parameter *a* abruptly changes to the *a* values of pure Ir MEA. The Ir-Ru 50:50 hcp lattice parameter *c* slowly returns to the original value at the beginning of the procedure after a sharp increment, while the parameter *a* remains constant.

The phase composition of the fcc and hcp phases, plotted in Figures 7 and 8, respectively, includes the platinum phase, which was considered stable during the fitting. Therefore, the sum of the plotted Ir fcc and Ru hcp phase is not equal to 1. Assuming small or no changes in the Pt fcc phase, it is a good measure of the total amount of the probed fcc and hcp crystalline phases of Ir-Ru. The interpretation is reasonably straightforward for the Ir 100 sample; the total amount of fcc (here only Ir) phase steadily decreases over the procedure, as one can see in Figure 7. This indicates that the crystalline Ir is oxidizing into typically amorphous electrochemical oxides,^[67] which also confirms that the catalyst is active and connected. The situation is more complicated for bimetallic samples Ir-Ru 50:50 and Ir-Ru 25:75, where the amount of the hcp phase continuously decreases (Figure 8). In contrast, the amount of the fcc phase shows an initial increase followed by a decrease. This can be easily explained by Ru being less stable; therefore, it is oxidizing/dissolving much faster than Ir; consequently, the relative amount of Ir is increasing. Specifically, the relative amount of the fcc phase for Ir-Ru 50:50 abruptly increases at the beginning of the procedure, corresponding to the initial quick dissolution of Ru, after which it remains relatively stable. Simultaneously, the hcp phase of Ir-Ru 50:50 rapidly decreases. On the other hand, the relative amount of the fcc phase of Ir-Ru 25:75 slightly increases throughout the procedure, reflecting the slow decrement of the hcp phase. The total phase content comparison (Ir, Ru, Pt) might be confusing; therefore, we include the evolution of the hcp phase alone relative to the fcc phase without Pt in Figure S23 (Supporting Information).

The evolution of the phases supports our previous core-shell model: MEA Ir-Ru 25:75 remains relatively stable as the majority of the catalyst stays protected by the Ir shell, formed after the quick initial dissolution of the unprotected Ru, which maintains the strain in the catalyst. However, the shell is not formed as efficiently in MEA Ir-Ru 50:50, resulting in a significant change in the lattice parameter of the fcc phase, as the Ru from the surrounding hcp phase is dissolved much more efficiently, causing very little change in the hcp lattice parameters, but a huge relative drop of the hcp phase content at the same time.

The evolution of the crystallite size is discussed in the Figures S24 and S25 (Supporting Information). The edge-land data show the same trends as the middle-land data (Figure S26, Supporting Information), which excludes possible radiation damage as a typical concern during the operando measurements.^[68] Moreover, the comparison shows that the middle-land is better electrically connected than the edge-land (more details are provided in SI).

2.7. The Microscopy Study of the Ir-Ru catalyst

The morphology of all samples was comparable when viewed by SEM and TEM; the example of overall morphology at BOL is shown in Figures S8 (SEM) and Figure S9 (Supporting Information) (TEM). The processing of the HR-TEM images is generally complicated in our system.^[69] Due to the large possible amounts of present species (Ir fcc, Ir hcp, Ru fcc, Ru hcp, possibly IrO₂ and RuO₂, etc.), observable under different orientations ([111], [110], etc.), it is challenging to directly distinguish for example hcp Ir and hcp Ru, which are structurally almost identical. Therefore, instead of aiming for a direct sample comparison, we describe only HR-TEM images of Ir-Ru 25:75 in Figure 9a,b. Practically, we observe many crystalline particles, which confirms our observations by XPS and WAXS. Crystallinity can be confirmed using FFT (Figure S28, Supporting Information). The HR-TEM images confirm that the typical size of the crystallites at BOL corresponds very well to our WAXS observation (5–6 nm in Figures S24 and S25, Supporting Information). Moreover, in Figure 9a, we see that the nature of the magnetron sputtered Ir-Ru 25:75 catalyst is a mixture of fcc and hcp particles in proximity.

3. Discussion of the Ir-Ru system

3.1. Formation of the Ir-Ru@IrOx

Our current understanding of the Ir-Ru system is as follows: An Ir-Ru catalyst is initially formed as a thin film by magnetron co-sputtering on a sputter-etched structure on PEM. The resulting catalyst does not exhibit any specific layered or core-shell structure. Due to the character of magnetron co-sputtering,^[70] it has areas with slightly higher Ir or Ru content. However, Ir and Ru are generally alloying and mutually affecting their lattice parameters, following Vegard's law. Because of the strain induced by hcp Ru, the Ir in contact with the Ru can be also in the hcp phase or strongly strained toward it. Immediately when the potential is applied, a massive dissolution of almost all unprotected Ru occurs, completely depleting Ru from the very surface of the catalyst in accordance with the Ru thermodynamics.^[52] Those abrupt initial changes explain the significantly higher degradation rates observed in Table 1, compared to our previous studies,^[22] together

Figure 9. HR-TEMs from Ir-Ru 25:75 sample at BOL with measured distances of crystalline planes and angles between them a) lower magnification, b) higher magnification detail of one crystallite.

with the component (LDGL, etc.) effect. The Ru dissolution leads to the dynamic formation of a protective Ir shell on an Ir-Ru core. The Ir shell demonstrates much better activity than typically observed for the pure Ir-based catalyst.^[20,22,67,71]

3.2. Activity of Ir-Ru@IrO_x

The superior performance of the Ir-Ru samples can be attributed to the unique characteristics of the Ir shell. SRPES analysis reveals that the Ir shell, in the form of Ir^{III} and Ir^{IV} oxides, is \approx 1 nm thick. Both XPS and SRPES analyses indicate that the Ir shell in the Ir-Ru samples is significantly less oxidized compared to the pure Ir 100 sample. This occurs despite the morphological effect, where Ru leaching in the Ir-Ru samples is expected to expose more Ir surface area. Literature suggests that this phenomenon is due to the increasing electronegativity of Ir as Ru content increases, coupled with a downward shift of the center of the Ir 5d band. This shift has been theoretically linked to the enhanced activity of the Ir-Ru bimetallic system with an IrO_x surface layer^[38] and can relate to the observed compressive strain on Ir, which lowers the corresponding interatomic distances. The lower 5d band center results in weakened bonding between Ir and oxygenated OER intermediates (*OH, *O, *OOH), thereby enhancing OER activity.^[33,72] Moreover, the lower oxidation state of Ir is generally associated with higher catalytic activity even in the systems without Ru.^[34,53,54] However, these oxidation states are typically unstable under OER conditions, which often limits the performance of Ir catalysts.^[42,67,71] In the case of Ir-Ru samples, the combination of Ru and the strain in the catalyst structure helps stabilize the lower oxidation states of Ir, and thus prevents

the formation of the Ir species^[42,67,71] connected with degradation. The obtained electrochemical results strongly support our hypothesis, as we consistently observe a lower Tafel slope in the Ir-Ru systems compared to pure Ir. Since a properly measured Tafel slope is independent of the number of active sites,^[73] this change cannot be explained by the increase of the active surface area due to the Ru leaching out, rather it suggests a fundamentally different surface mechanism in Ir-Ru catalysts compared to Ir 100.

3.3. Stability Ir-Ru@IrO_x

From the operando WAXS measurements, we observe that the compressive strain on Ir in the Ir-Ru 50:50 catalyst is lost very quickly at the beginning of the procedure. This indicates that the increased electronegativity effect of Ir disappears early in the process. This correlates well with the XPS results, where the oxidation levels of Ir in the surface layer (sampling depth: 5.3 nm) follow the trend: Ir 100 (67%) > Ir-Ru 50:50 (59%) > Ir-Ru 25:75 (42%). A similar trend is seen in the SRPES samples (Figure S17 and Table S4, Supporting Information), suggesting that excessive oxidation in the Ir-Ru 50:50 sample is related to the loss of strain and Ru, leading to faster degradation of Ir due to its lower loading and disrupted structure. While the loss of activity is a gradual process, typically observed over days in single-cell PEM-WE tests,^[20] it is not immediately apparent in shorter operando WAXS studies (Figure 1; Table S1, Supporting Information), where degradation rates fluctuate due to the ongoing break-in process. However, this helps explain the previously observed instability of Ir-Ru 50:50.^[20] A key observation from the operando measurements

is that the loss of strain occurs rapidly upon potential application. This indicates that the Ir-Ru system is highly sensitive to the break-in electrochemical procedure. If the Ir-Ru structure forms without issues and remains stable, the resulting Ir-Ru@IrO_x catalyst should exhibit exceptional stability, with stability per loading outperforming pure Ir. This is because Ir degradation is typically associated with oxidation to higher states.^[67,71,74] Notably, the Ir-Ru 25:75 composition after the 4-h operando procedure (72% Ir, 28% Ru) closely matches that obtained after 1272 h of continuous operation (69% Ir, 31% Ru), demonstrating that the core-shell structure does not significantly change after it is properly formed.^[22] Consequently, the initial changes in strain may serve as a useful indicator of long-term stability in Ir-Ru and other bimetallic Ir-M systems.

4. Conclusion

In this study, we examined the performance and underlying mechanisms of Ir 100, Ir-Ru 50:50, Ir-Ru 25:75, and Ru 100 catalysts in a dedicated PEM-WE cell using high-energy synchrotron radiation for WAXS measurements. After correcting for Ohmic resistance and double-layer capacitance, we demonstrated that the electrochemical performances in the operando cell are comparable to those in standard PEM-WE measurements. Through operando WAXS and a comprehensive range of ex situ techniques (XPS, SRPES, HR-TEM, EDX), we revealed that the Ir-Ru catalysts form a dynamic Ir-Ru@IrO_x core-shell structure with a Ru-depleted surface. The Ru-rich core induces strain in the surrounding Ir, potentially driving it into the hcp phase. This strain increases the electronegativity of Ir, stabilizing it in lower oxidation states, which leads to improved activity and stability compared to pure Ir catalysts.

We explained the superior activity and stability of Ir-Ru 25:75 compared to Ir-Ru 50:50 by the incomplete protection of the Ru and the Ir-Ru strain in Ir-Ru 50:50. Here, the strain caused by Ru dissipated quickly at the start of the procedure, resulting in greater Ir oxidation at EOL and explaining its poorer stability in single cell.^[20] This effect may be procedure-dependent, as different activation protocols could influence shell formation—our approach involved the immediate application of a high potential (1.6–1.7 V) to the catalyst. In summary, we elucidated the reasons behind the enhanced activity and stability of the Ir-Ru 25:75 catalyst. Given that Ru does not directly participate in the electrochemical reaction, we propose that other materials (M) could be used in the core of the Ir-M@IrO_x structure. This opens up new possibilities for replacing the noble, costly Ru with non-noble alternatives such as Co or Ti, which could significantly reduce catalyst costs.^[75]

5. Experimental Section

Membrane Electrode Assemblies (MEAs) Preparation: Nafion membranes NR 212 (50.8 μm, Chemours) were used as a PEM for all prepared samples. The anode sides of the PEM-WE were entirely prepared by magnetron sputtering. Initially, the PEM was etched using the sputter-etching process to enhance the active surface area and mitigate issues related to thin film cracking.^[15] Subsequently, the modified layers were covered by the catalytic layers with varying concentrations of Ir-Ru (Ir 100, Ir-Ru 50:50, Ir-Ru 25:75, Ru 100) as in.^[20] The layer thicknesses were

equivalent to 130 nm of the deposit on a flat support for all samples, as verified by Atomic Force Microscope (AFM) using the varnish droplet method.^[76] The details of those processes can be found in the previous publications.^[22] The Ir-Ru layers were contacted by a sintered Ti Liquid Gas Diffusion Layer (LGDL, Mott). No Pt was used for Ti protection to prevent Pt signal overlap with the Ir signal during WAXS measurements. For the cathode, a commercial Gas Diffusion Electrode was used (GDE, Pt, 0.5 mg cm⁻², Fuel Cell Store). Table 2 summarizes the prepared samples. The loadings of noble metals were calculated assuming that the density of Ir and Ru equals the bulk values. Since the actual density of the magnetron-sputtered layers was lower,^[77] this value corresponds to the upper estimation of the loadings.

Physico-Chemical Analysis: All samples were characterized outside of the PEM-WE cell (dry), both at the Beginning Of Life (BOL) before inserting into the cell and at the End Of Life (EOL) after the standard electrochemical procedure, defined later. The elemental composition was measured using Energy Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) by XFlash 6/10 EDX detector, incorporated into a Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) device. Measurements were conducted with a primary electron energy of 6 keV, covering the M-lines of Ir and Ru to achieve maximum surface sensitivity.^[78] Even with this energy, the information depth was equal to several hundreds of nm, allowing EDX to measure the overall elemental composition of the entire Ir-Ru layer volume.^[79] The spectra were processed by standard PBZAF approximation to obtain the elemental composition.^[78]

X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) was a complementary method to EDX. Due to the low mean free path of the outgoing low energetic photoelectrons (hundreds of eVs), this technique provides information only from the actual surface of the catalyst (1–5 nm).^[80] Moreover, by properly fitting the XPS spectra, the elemental composition and the chemical state of the measured elements can be estimated.^[81] These properties make XPS a perfect method for investigating surfaces of heterogeneous catalysts.^[82] The XPS measurements were conducted using EnviroESCA device (Specs) with a monochromatized Al K_α source (1486.71 eV). Signal detection was performed using a Phoibos 150 NAP 1D-DLD (Specs) hemispherical analyzer in Fixed Analyzer Transmission (FAT) regime. The EnviroESCA device allowed us to focus on a precise area of 300 μm², enabling us to perform XPS at the same spots on the samples as for the EDX analysis to reduce possible inhomogeneity effects. Ir 4f, Ru 3d, C 1s, and O 1s core levels were measured. The number of scans was set to achieve a sufficient signal-to-noise ratio. Charging correction was done by leveling the Fermi edge to 0 eV, if it was distinguishable (BOL samples) or leveling the C 1s to 284.3 eV if not.^[83] This precise C 1s value (284.3 eV) was determined by comparing metallic Ir and Ru positions. Fitting was performed using KolXP software (Kolibri); the metallic states and the conductive oxides were fitted by Doniach–Šunjić profiles convoluted with Gaussian to account for the asymmetric behavior of these states.^[84] The remaining states and satellites were fitted by a symmetric Voigt profile.^[85] This approach seems to work best to compensate the states asymmetry.^[86] Shirley's background was subtracted for the core-level spectra, while linear background was subtracted to fit the Fermi Edge.^[87] High-resolution Synchrotron Radiation PhotoElectron Spectroscopy (SRPES) experiments were performed at the Materials Science Beamline (MSB), the Elettra synchrotron light facility in Trieste, Italy. The MSB was equipped with a bending magnet source providing synchrotron light in the energy range of 21–1000 eV. All measurements were conducted in the UHV end-station with a multichannel electron energy analyzer (Specs Phoibos 150) without additional sample manipulation.

Morphological analysis was conducted using a SEM device, Mira III (Tescan), and Transmission Electron Microscopes (TEM) JEOL JEM 2200 FS and JEOL JEM NEOARM-200F. The primary electron energy in SEM was 6 keV to minimize polymer PEM charging and damage and to ensure compatibility with EDX. The view field was 300 μm² at which several images were taken for each sample to assess the general morphology at the BOL and EOL. The TEM was used in High Resolution (HR-TEM) mode with the primary energy of the electrons being 200 keV and scanning mode (STEM) with a high-angle annular dark field detector. EDX element maps were acquired using a JEOL JED-2300 analyzer. Thin lamellas for the TEM study were made using the lift-out technique,

Figure 10. Scheme of the operando WAXS procedure for PEM-WE. The procedure consists of three parts: starting PEIS at OCV (cyan), current steps with PEIS (light blue), and long stability (violet). The WAXS scans at the middle land and edge land are marked with orange and light orange, respectively.

utilizing Ga^+ Focused Ion Beam (FIB) of a Tescan LYRA dual beam microscope.

Structural Analysis: Synchrotron WAXS measurements were performed at the ID31 beamline at ESRF in Grenoble, France. X-ray energy was set to 75 keV to be below the Ir K-edge and thus minimize fluorescence.^[88] The samples from Table 2 were measured both ex situ and in *operando*. Ex situ measurements were conducted in a transmission regime with a defocused X-ray beam (≈ 1 mm diameter) on the PEM membrane with the catalytic layers. The *operando* measurements were performed in “grazing incidence” mode using a dedicated X-ray transparent cell, as described in detail in the publication,^[43] with an active surface area of 0.64 cm^2 . The cell design allows the X-ray beam to slice the catalytic layer of interest parallel to the membrane, which reduces the noise from LGDL and the catalyst on the cathode. For the *operando* measurements, the beam was intensively focused on the catalytic layer ($5 \mu\text{m}$ in the vertical direction). Each sample was aligned prior to the measurements to maximize the signal from the Ir-Ru layer of interest. The scattered signal was detected by a Dectris Pilatus CdTe 2 M detector positioned 50 cm behind the sample. The energy, detector distance, and tilts were estimated using a calibration CeO_2 powder sample (NIST); consequently, the measured 2D diffraction patterns were reduced to the standard 1D diffractograms using the pyFAI package.^[89]

The *operando* measurements consisted of scans (1 scan corresponds to a series of diffractograms separated in space, acquired at a specific time) conducted at discrete times throughout the electrochemical procedure to capture the evolution of the structural state of the catalytic layer. Each of those scans consisted of 60 separated frames (1 frame corresponding to 1 WAXS diffractogram) at 60 different positions, separated by $5 \mu\text{m}$ along the vertical axis perpendicular to the expected position of the catalytic layer (Figure S29, Supporting Information). The large range of the scanning (compared to the thickness of the catalyst) was performed to consider possible movements of the membrane during operation. In the postprocessing of the data, the frame with the highest signal from the catalytic layer was chosen for each scan, averaged with the two closest frames, and used for further analysis.

The averaged XRD with the best Ir-Ru signals from each scan were processed by Rietveld refinement using GSAS II software.^[90] The phases of Ir mp-101,^[55] Ru mp-33,^[56] and Pt mp-126^[91] were fitted if the respected element was present in the sample (i.e., no Ru phase in MEA Ir 100, etc.). The fitting was done at a higher 2θ range (6.5° to 13°) to avoid signals from the cell, water, and non-crystalline phases, appearing at lower 2θ ranges. The Pt phase was fitted as well since some Pt signal was visible due to imperfect alignment of the tilt of the PEM-WE cell and possible bending of the whole MEA structure; however, as expected, no significant structural changes in the commercial Pt catalyst during HER have been observed. In

the case of the ex situ measurements, a multiplication of the signal from the plain etched PEM was used as the background, while inverse Chebyshev polynomials^[90] were used for the operando measurements.

Electrochemical Procedure with Operando WAXS: The electrochemical processes were measured in a dedicated X-ray transparent cell for *operando* PEM-WE with an active area of 0.64 cm^2 (circular area with a diameter of 9 mm).^[43] The cell was connected to a BioLogic Sp-240 potentiostat and kept at 50°C by the flow of preheated water. The electrochemical procedure was designed to simulate the operation of PEM-WE and was summarized in Figure 10. Before any measurements, Potential Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (PEIS, from 10 kHz to 100 mHz, 10 mV amplitude, 6 points per decade) at Open Circuit Voltage (OCV) was measured to check the electrical connection and ohmic resistance without inducing any electrochemical changes. Afterwards, galvanostatic steps from 100 to 600 mA cm^{-2} were performed. Each step lasted 10 min, and between the scans, a set of PEIS measurements was done at voltages of 1.44, 1.48, 1.52, 1.56, and 1.6 V. The last part of the electrochemical procedure consisted of a long galvanostatic stability at 300 mA cm^{-2} . In total, the entire procedure lasted for 3.5 h. The *operando* WAXS measurements were synchronized with the electrochemistry by a triggering between the detector and the potentiostat; consequently, they were measured at the same moment of the procedure, as shown in Figure 10: 1 scan at OCV conditions at the beginning; 5 scans during each galvanostatic step, 3 of them under potential, 2 at OCV conditions; and 20 scans during the long stability at 300 mA cm^{-2} . The scans were measured at two positions (as defined in Figure S30, Supporting Information) to check the possible effects of radiation damage and to increase the statistical reliability of the obtained data: the first one under the center of the flow field ridge/land (labeled as middle land) and the second one shifted by $150 \mu\text{m}$ to the edge of the land (edge land). The second position (edge land) was measured here to reduce an error from the PEM movement during the experiment. The catalyst was not measured underneath the channels of the flow field due to the significant movements of the membrane therein. Except for the first BOL scan, the scans were sorted in batches of 5. Within every 5 scans, 1st, 3rd, and 5th scans were done at the middle land and 2nd and 4th at the edge land. The overall radiation that affected the edge land position was thus only 2/5 of the one in the middle land.

PEIS data were fitted using RelaxIS software with the equivalent electrical circuits.^[92] A standard Randles equivalent electrical circuit was used for the anode; the impedance response of the cathode was omitted as negligible due to the fast kinetics of HER.^[93] Therefore, the fitted circuit was $R_o-(R_a)(CPE_a)$ (Figure S31, Supporting Information) with the fitted elements: Ohmic resistance (R_o), charge transfer resistance of the anode (R_a), and constant phase element of the anode (CPE_a), also known as pseudo capacitance.^[94]

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in [Zenodo] at [https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13348108], reference number [13348108].

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